

Kaup, C. F. (2022):

Codebook to the article: A Cultural-Historical Perspective on How Double Stimulation Triggers Expansive Learning.

Expansive learning

Questioning

Q1: Challenging participants into questioning

Q2: Criticizing existing practice

Q3: Questioning the proposed development

Analyzing

A1: Articulating needs and ideas

A2: Historical analysis

A3: Articulating problems or challenges

A4: Identifying contradictions

A5: Weighing alternative solutions

A6: Analyzing implemented curricular units

A7: Interpretation of rules and policies

Modelling

M1: Sketching the initial idea of a model

M2: Naming and defining the model

M3: Fixing the model in material or graphic form

M4: Varying and adapting the model

M5: Ideation for concrete curricular units

M6: Ideation for redesign of implemented curricular units

Examining

E1: Discussing the model critically

E2: Enriching the model

E3: Analysing not yet implemented curricular units

Implementing

I1: Reporting on the use of designed curricular units

I2: Evaluation of implemented curricular units

Reflecting on the process

R1: Reflections on activities in the process

R2: Reflections on personal professional development

Consolidating and generalizing

C1: Articulating and summarizing outcomes

C2: Discussing ideas for generalisations

C3: Preparing dissemination activities

Non expansive learning action

N1: Informing

N2: Summarizing

N3: Clarifying

N4: Isolated episode

N5: Planning for implementation of curricular units

Questioning

Questions previous activities - by analyzing or pointing out problematic situations

Analyzing

Analysis of systematic and historical causes in relation to the problem identified
Resolves and models internal contradictions of the activity system and activity that cause the problem. Attempts to uncover why and how they do what they do

Modeling

Looking at the systematic structure of activity to find new forms of activity that can create expansive ways of resolving inner tensions
Finding new ways to interpret the purpose of the activity (the object) and a new logic of the organization.
Create a new model of activity. Look at how concrete learning materials can be targeted to the object or redesigned.

Examining

Discuss the model critically or enrich it from new angles or with new knowledge/new ways of solving it. Analysis of non-implemented content.

Implementing

Concretization of the new model. Which changes to test next time, take the first steps into practice and evaluate them. Start transforming practice by designing and implementing new tools and solutions.

Reflection

Reflection on the activity, including competence development

Consolidating and generalizing

Start teaching others what we have learned - it becomes a regular part of practice.

Double stimulation

- Phase 1: a problem related to the object of the activity, or the unit of analysis observed by the researcher or the participant.
- Phase 2: a conflict of motives articulated by the researcher or the participant and dealing with the object of the activity.
- Phase 3: a possible auxiliary motive that helps to overcome the problem in Phases 1 or 2 such as an idea or a concept, etc.
- Phase 4: A plan for implementation of the model, which could be coordination of the process or who should complete certain tasks related to the object of the activity.

When one of the four phases occurs in a new learning action, then it is count again.

References

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